

Convertible Bond Study with Jump-Diffusion

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a model for pricing convertible bond. The model relies on the probability distribution of a default jump rather than the default jump itself. In a typical convertible bond arbitrage strategy, the arbitrageur entails purchasing a convertible bond and selling the underlying stock to create a delta neutral position. Delta neutral hedging is great for uncertain stocks that are expected to make huge breakouts in either direction. Since convertible bonds are issued mainly by start-up or small companies, the chance of a large movement in either direction is very likely. Even for very small movements in the underlying stock price, profits can still be generated from the yield of the convertible bond and the interest rebate for the short position.

Key Words: jump diffusion, convertible bond, convertible underpricing, convertible arbitrage, default time approach, default probability approach, asset pricing and credit risk modeling.

1. Introduction

There is a rich literature on the subject of convertible bonds. Arguably, the first widely adopted model among practitioners is the one presented by Goldman Sachs (1994) and then formalized by Tsiveriotis and Fernandes (1998). The Goldman Sachs' solution is a simple one factor model with an equity binomial tree to value convertible bonds. The model considers the probability of conversion at every node. If the convertible is certain to remain a bond, it is then discounted by a risky discount rate that reflects the credit risk of the issuer. If the convertible is certain to be converted, it is then discounted by the risk-free interest rate that is equivalent to default free.

Grimwood and Hodges (2002) indicate that the Goldman Sachs model is incoherent because it assumes that bonds are susceptible to credit risk but equities are not. Ayache, et al. (2003) conclude that the Tsiveriotis-Fernandes model is inherently unsatisfactory due to its unrealistic assumption of stock prices being unaffected by bankruptcy. To correct this weakness, Davis and Lischka (1999), Andersen and Buffum (2004), Bloomberg (2009), and Carr and Linetsky (2006) etc., propose a jump-diffusion model to explore defaultable stock price dynamics. They all believe that under a risk-neutral measure the expected rate of return on a defaultable stock must be equal to the risk-free interest rate. The jump-diffusion model characterizes the default time/jump directly.

There are two primary types of models that attempt to describe default processes in the literature: structural models and reduced-form models. The structural models regard default as an endogenous event, focusing on the capital structure of a firm. The reduced-form models do not explain the event of a default endogenously, but instead characterize it exogenously as a jump process. Many practitioners in the credit trading arena have tended to gravitate toward the reduced-form models given their mathematical tractability and market consistency.

Although both the structural jump-diffusion model and the reduced-form model contain jumps, these jumps have different meanings: A jump in the structural jump-diffusion model corresponds to a

sudden change in the asset value that may or may not cause the firm to default, whereas a jump in the reduced-form model represents the default event itself.

Although we agree that under a risk-neutral measure the market price of risk and risk preferences are irrelevant to asset pricing (see Hull (2003)) and thereby the expectation of a risk-free¹ asset grows at the risk-free interest rate, we are not convinced that the expected rate of return on a defaultable asset must be also equal to the risk-free rate. We argue that unlike market risk, credit risk actually has a significant impact on asset prices. This is why regulators, such as International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS), etc. require financial institutions to report a credit value adjustment (CVA) in addition to the risk-free mark-to-market (MTM) value to reflect credit risk (see Xiao (2013)). By definition, a CVA is the difference between the risk-free value and the risky value of an asset/portfolio subject to credit risk. CVA implies that the risk-free value should not be equal to the risky value in the presence of default risk. As a matter of fact, we will prove that the expected return of a defaultable asset under a risk-neutral measure actually grows at a risky rate rather than the risk-free rate. This conclusion is very important for risky valuation.

This article makes a theoretical and empirical contribution to the study of convertible bonds. In contrast to the above mentioned literature, we present a model that is based on the probability distribution (or intensity) of a default jump (or a default time) rather than the default jump itself, as the default jump is usually inaccessible (see Duffie and Huang (1996), Jarrow and Protter (2004), etc).

Valuation under our risky model can be solved by common numerical methods, such as, Monte Carlo simulation, tree/lattice approaches, or partial differential equation (PDE) solutions. The PDE algorithm is elaborated in this paper, but of course the methodology can be easily extended to tree/lattice or Monte Carlo.

The most important input parameter to be determined is the volatility for valuation. A common approach in the market is to use the at-the-money (ATM) implied Black-Scholes volatility to price

¹ Here, *risk-free* means free of credit risk, but not necessarily of market risk

convertible bonds. However, most liquid stock options have relatively short maturates (rarely more than 8 years). As a result, some authors, such as Ammann, et al. (2003), Loncarski, et al. (2009), Zabolotnyuk, et al. (2010), have to make do with historical volatilities. Therefore, we segment the sample into two sets according to the time to maturity: a short-maturity class (0 ~ 8 years) and a long-maturity class (> 8 years). For the short-maturity class, we use the ATM implied Black-Scholes volatilities for valuation, whereas for the long-maturity class, we calculate the historical volatility as the annualized standard deviation of the daily log returns of the last 2 years and then price the convertible bond based on this real-world volatility.

It is useful to examine the basics of the convertible arbitrage strategy. A typical convertible bond arbitrage employs delta-neutral hedging, in which an arbitrageur buys a convertible bond and sells the underlying equity at the current delta (see Choi, et al. (2009), Loncarski, et al. (2009), etc.). With delta neutral positions, the sign of Gamma is important. If Gamma is negative, the portfolio profits so long as the underlying equity remains stable. If Gamma is positive, the portfolio will profit from large movements in the stock price in either direction (see Somanath (2011)).

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: The model is presented in Section 2. Section 3 elaborates the PDE approach; Section 4 discusses the empirical results. The conclusions are provided in Section 5. PDE implementation details, a binomial tree approach and a comparison of models are contained in the appendices.

2 Model

From a practitioner's perspective, Monte Carlo is a "last resort" and "least preferred" method, whereas lattice or PDE approaches suffer from the curse of dimensionality: The number of evaluations and computational cost increase exponentially with the dimension of the problem, making it impractical to use in more than two dimensions.

We consider a filtered probability space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}, \mathcal{P})$ satisfying the usual conditions, where Ω denotes a sample space, \mathcal{F} denotes a σ -algebra, \mathcal{P} denotes a probability measure, and $\{\mathcal{F}_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ denotes a filtration.

The risk-free stock price process can be described as

$$dS(t) = r(t)S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) \quad (1)$$

where $S(t)$ denotes the stock price, $r(t)$ denotes the risk-free interest rate, σ denotes the volatility, $W(t)$ denotes a Wiener process.

The expectation of equation (1) is

$$E(dS(t)|\mathcal{F}_t) = r(t)S(t)dt \quad (2)$$

where $E\{\bullet|\mathcal{F}_t\}$ is the expectation conditional on the \mathcal{F}_t .

Next, we turn to a defaultable stock. The defaultable stock process proposed by Davis and Lischka (1999), Andersen and Buffum (2004), and Bloomberg (2009), etc., is given by

$$dS(t) = (r(t) + h(t))S(t_-)dt + \hat{\sigma}S(t_-)dW(t) - S(t_-)dU(t) \quad (3)$$

where $U(t)$ is an independent Poisson process with $dU(t) = 1$ with probability $h(t)dt$ and 0 otherwise, $h(t)$ is the hazard rate or the default intensity, $S(t_-)$ is the stock price immediately before any jump at time t . The expectation of $dU(t)$ is $E(dU(t)|\mathcal{F}_t) = h(t)dt$.

The expectation of equation (3) is given by

$$E(dS(t)|\mathcal{F}_t) = (r(t) + h(t))S(t)dt - S(t)h(t)dt = r(t)S(t)dt \quad (4)$$

The jump-diffusion model was first proposed in the context of market risk, which naturally exhibits high skewness and leptokurtosis levels and captures the so-called implied volatility smile or skew effects. Ederington and Lee (1993) find that the markets tend to have overreaction and underreaction to the outside news. The jump part of the model can be interpreted as the market response to outside news. If there is not any outside news, the asset price changes according to a geometric Brownian motion. Since the market

price of risk and risk preferences are irrelevant to asset pricing within the market risk context, the expected rate of return to the stockholders is equal to the risk-free rate under a risk-neutral measure.

The world of credit modeling is divided into two main approaches: structural models and reduced-form (or intensity) models. The structural models regard default as an endogenous event, focusing on the capital structure of a firm. The reduced-form models do not explain the event of default endogenously, but instead characterize it exogenously as a jump process. In general, structural models are based on the information set available to the firm's management, such as the firm's assets and liabilities; while reduced-form models are based on the information set available to the market, such as the firm's bond prices or credit default swap (CDS) premia. Many practitioners in the credit trading arena have tended to gravitate toward the reduced-form models given their mathematical tractability. The reduced-form models can be made consistent with the risk-neutral probabilities of default backed out from corporate bond prices or CDS spreads/premia.

In the reduced-form models, the stopping (or default) time τ of a firm is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default and is defined as,

$$\tau = \inf \left\{ t : \int_0^t h(s, \Phi_s) ds \geq \Delta \right\} \quad (5)$$

where $h(t)$ or $h(t, \Phi_t)$ denotes the stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity dependent on an exogenous common state Φ_t , and Δ is a unit exponential random variable independent of Φ_t .

It is well-known that the survival probability from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$p(t, s) := P(\tau > s \mid \tau > t, Z) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (6)$$

The default probability for the period (t, s) in this framework is defined by

$$q(t, s) := P(\tau \leq s \mid \tau > t, Z) = 1 - p(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (7)$$

The DTA involves the default time explicitly. If there has been no default before time T (i.e., $\tau > T$), the value of the asset at T is $V(T)$. If a default happens before T (i.e., $t < \tau \leq T$), a recovery payoff is made at the default time τ as a fraction of the market value² given by $\varphi V(\tau)$ where φ is the default recovery rate and $V(\tau)$ is the market value at default. Under a risk-neutral measure, the value of this defaultable asset is the discounted expectation of all the payoffs and is given by

$$V(t) = E\left[\left(D(t, T)V(T)1_{\tau > T} + D(t, \tau)\varphi V(\tau)1_{\tau \leq T}\right) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (8)$$

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise, and $D(t, \tau)$ denotes the stochastic risk-free discount factor at t for the maturity τ given by

$$D(t, \tau) = \exp\left[-\int_t^\tau r(u)du\right] \quad (9)$$

The DPA relies on the probability distribution of the default time rather than the default time itself. We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period. In our derivation, we use the approximation $\exp(y) \approx 1 + y$ for very small y . The survival and default probabilities for the period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ are given by

$$\hat{p}(t) := p(t, t + \Delta t) = \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx 1 - h(t)\Delta t \quad (10)$$

$$\hat{q}(t) := q(t, t + \Delta t) = 1 - \exp(-h(t)\Delta t) \approx h(t)\Delta t \quad (11)$$

The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. For the one-period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ economy, at time $t + \Delta t$ the asset either defaults with the default probability $q(t, t + \Delta t)$ or survives with the survival probability $p(t, t + \Delta t)$. The survival payoff is equal to the market value $V(t + \Delta t)$ and the default payoff is a fraction of the market value: $\varphi(t + \Delta t)V(t + \Delta t)$. Under a risk-neutral measure, the value of the asset at t is the expectation of all the payoffs discounted at the risk-free rate and is given by

² Here we use the recovery of market value (RMV) assumption.

$$V(t) = E\left\{\exp(-r(t)\Delta t)[\hat{p}(t) + \varphi(t)\hat{q}(t)]V(t + \Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \approx E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)V(t + \Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (12)$$

where $y(t) = r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi(t)) = r(t) + c(t)$ denotes the risky rate and $c(t) = h(t)(1 - \varphi(t))$ is called the (short) credit spread.

Similarly, we have

$$V(t + \Delta t) = E\left\{\exp(-y(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right\} \quad (13)$$

Note that $\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)$ is $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable. By definition, an $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable random variable is a random variable whose value is known at time $t + \Delta t$. Based on the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V(t) &= E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)V(t + \Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{\exp(-y(t)\Delta t)E\left[\exp(-y(t + \Delta t)\Delta t)V(t + 2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right]|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= E\left\{\exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^1 y(t + i\Delta t)\Delta t\right)V(t + 2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

By recursively deriving from t forward over T and taking the limit as Δt approaches zero, the risky value of the asset can be expressed as

$$V(t) = E\left\{\exp\left[-\int_t^T y(u)du\right]V(T)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \quad (15)$$

The derivation of equation (15) takes into account all credit characteristics: possibility of a jump to default and recovery rate. It tells us that a defaultable asset under the risk-neutral measure grows at a *risky rate*. The risky rate is equal to a risk-free interest rate plus a credit spread. If the asset is a bond, the equation is the same as Equation (10) in Duffie and Singleton (1999), which is the market model for pricing risky bonds. The market bond model says that the value of a risky bond is obtained by discounting the promised payoff using the risk-free interest rate plus the credit spread³.

In asset pricing theory, the fundamental no-arbitrage theorems do not require expected returns to be equal to the risk free rate, but only that prices are martingales after discounting under the numeraire. For

³ There is a liquidity component in the bond spread. This paper, however, focuses on credit risk only.

risk-free valuation, people commonly use a risk-free bond as the numeraire, whereas for risky valuation, they should choose an associated risky numeraire to reflect credit risk. The expected return is that of the numeraire.

According to equation (15), we propose a risky model that embeds the probability of the default jump rather than the default jump itself into the price dynamics of an asset. The stochastic differential equation (SDE) of a defaultable stock is defined as

$$dS(t) = (r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t)))S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) = y(t)S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) \quad (16)$$

where φ_s is the recovery rate of the stock and $y(t) = r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t))$ is the risky rate.

Equation (16) is the direct derivation of equation (15). The formula allows different assumptions concerning recovery on default. In particular, $\varphi_s = 0$ represents the situation where the stock price jumps to 0, and $\varphi_s = 1$ corresponds to the risk-free case. The expectation of equations (16) is

$$E(dS(t)|\mathcal{F}_t) = (r(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t)))S(t)dt \quad (17)$$

3. PDE Algorithm

The defaultable stock price process is given by

$$dS(t) = (r(t) - q(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t)))S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) = \mu(t)S(t)dt + \sigma S(t)dW(t) \quad (18)$$

where $q(t)$ is the dividend and $\mu(t) = r(t) - q(t) + h(t)(1 - \varphi_s(t))$.

Suppose that $G(S, t)$ is some function of S and t . Applying Ito Lemma, we have

$$dG = \left(\mu S \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} + \frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial S^2} \right) dt + \sigma S \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} dW \quad (19)$$

Since the Wiener process underlying S and G are the same, we can construct the following portfolio so that the Wiener process can be eliminated.

$$X = G - S \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} \quad (20)$$

Therefore, we have

$$dX = dG - \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} dS = \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial S^2} \right) dt \quad (21)$$

In contrast to all previous studies, we believe that the defaultable equity should grow at the risky rate of the equity including dividends, whereas the equity part of the convertible bond should earn the risky rate of the equity excluding dividends, i.e.,

$$(r + h(1 - \varphi_s))Gdt - (r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s)) \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} Sdt = dX = \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial S^2} \right) dt \quad (22)$$

So that the PDE of the equity component is given by

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial S^2} + (r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s))S \frac{\partial G}{\partial S} - (r + h(1 - \varphi_s))G = 0 \quad (23)$$

Similarly applying Ito Lemma to the bond part of the convertible $B(S, t)$, we obtain

$$dB = \left(\mu S \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} + \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial S^2} \right) dt + \sigma S \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} dW \quad (24)$$

Let us construct a portfolio so that we can eliminate the Wiener process as follows

$$Y = B - S \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} \quad (25)$$

Thus, we have

$$dY = dB - \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} dS = \left(\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial S^2} \right) dt \quad (26)$$

The defaultable equity should grow at the risky rate of the equity including dividends, while the bond part of the convertible bond grows at the risky rate of the bond. Consequently, we have

$$(r + h(1 - \varphi_b))Bdt - (r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s)) \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} Sdt = dY = \left(\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial S^2} \right) dt \quad (27)$$

where φ_b is the recovery rate of the bond.

The PDE of the bond component is

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} \sigma^2 S^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial S^2} + (r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s))S \frac{\partial B}{\partial S} - (r + h(1 - \varphi_b))B = 0 \quad (28)$$

The final conditions at maturity T can be generalized as

$$G_T = \begin{cases} \eta S_T, & \text{if } \eta S_T > \min[P_c, \max(P_p, N + C)] \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

$$B_T = \begin{cases} \min[P_c, \max(P_p, N + C)] & \text{if } \eta S_T \leq \min[P_c, \max(P_p, N + C)] \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (30)$$

where N denotes the bond principal, C denotes the coupon, P_c denotes the call price, P_p denotes the put price and η denotes the conversion ratio. The final conditions tell us that the convertible bond at the maturity is either a debt or an equity.

The upside constraints at time $t \in [0, T]$ are

$$\begin{cases} G_t = \eta S_t, B_t = 0 & \text{if } \eta S_t > \min[P_c, \max(P_p, \tilde{L}_t)] \\ G_t = 0, B_t = P_p & \text{else if } \tilde{L}_t \leq P_p \\ G_t = 0, B_t = P_c & \text{else if } \tilde{L}_t \geq P_c \\ G_t = \tilde{G}_t, B_t = \tilde{B}_t & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (31)$$

where $\tilde{L}_t = \tilde{B}_t + \tilde{G}_t$ is the continuation value of the convertible bond, \tilde{B}_t is the continuation value of the bond component and \tilde{G}_t is the continuation value of the equity component. Equation (31) says that the convertible is either in the continuation region or one of the three constraints (called, put or converted). One can use finite difference methods to solve the PDEs (23) and (28) for the price of a convertible bond.

4. Conclusion

Our study shows that risky asset pricing is quite different from risk-free asset pricing. In fact, the expectation of a defaultable asset actually grows at a risky rate rather than the risk-free rate. This conclusion is very important for risky valuation.

Empirically, we do not find evidence supporting a systematic underpricing hypothesis. We also find that convertible bonds have relatively large positive gammas, implying that convertible arbitrage can make a profit on a large upside and downside movement in the underlying stock price.

Appendix

A. Numeric implementation for PDE

In this section, we describe the numerical method used to solve discrete forms of (23) and (28). Let

$x = \ln\left(\frac{S_t}{S_0}\right)$ and define backward time as $\delta = T - t$. The equations (23) and (28) can be rewritten as

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial \delta} - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x^2} - \left(r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s) - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} + (r + h(1 - \varphi_b))B = 0 \quad (\text{A1})$$

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial \delta} - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 \frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial x^2} - \left(r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s) - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right) \frac{\partial G}{\partial x} + (r + h(1 - \varphi_s))G = 0 \quad (\text{A2})$$

The equations (A1) and (A2) can be approximated using Crank-Nicolson rule. We discretize the x to be equally spaced as a grid of nodes $0 \sim M$. At the maturity, G_T and B_T are determined according to (29) and (30). At any time $i+1$, the boundary conditions are

$$\begin{cases} B_0^{i+1}(1 + 0.5(r + h(1 - \varphi_b))\Delta\tau) = B_0^i(1 - 0.5(r + h(1 - \varphi_b))\Delta\tau) \\ G_0^{i+1}(1 + 0.5(r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s))\Delta\tau) = G_0^i(1 - 0.5(r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s))\Delta\tau) \end{cases} \quad \text{when } x \approx 0 \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\begin{cases} B_M^{i+1} = 0 \\ G_M^{i+1} = \eta S_M \end{cases} \quad \text{when } x \approx \infty \quad (\text{A4})$$

B. Binomial tree algorithm

A binomial tree method is equivalent to an explicit difference scheme. Suppose that the stock price S will either move up to the value uS with probability p_u or down to the value dS with probability $p_d = 1 - p_u$. As the binomial tree is a discrete approximation to the continuous distribution of equation (16), the expectation and variance of the discrete distribution should be equal to those of the continuous distribution. This method is commonly referred to as the moment matching technique.

To match the expectation, we have

$$E(S(t_{i+1})/S(t_i)) = p_u S(t_i)u + (1 - p_u)S(t_i)d = S(t_i)\exp(y_s \Delta t) \quad (\text{B1})$$

or

$$p_u u + (1 - p_u)d = \exp(y_s \Delta t) \quad (\text{B2})$$

where

$$y_s = r - q + c_s = r - q + h(1 - \varphi_s) \quad (\text{B3})$$

where q is the dividend.

To match the variance, we get

$$\text{Var}(S(t_{i+1})/S(t_i)) = S^2(t_i) [p_u u^2 + (1 - p_u) d^2 - \exp(2y_s \Delta t)] = S^2(t_i) \exp(2y_s \Delta t) (\exp(\sigma^2 \Delta t) - 1) \quad (\text{B4})$$

or

$$p_u u^2 + (1 - p_u) d^2 = \exp(2y_s \Delta t) \exp(\sigma^2 \Delta t) \quad (\text{B5})$$

Solving equations (B2) and (B5) according to the usual tree-symmetry condition: $u = 1/d$, we obtain

$$p_u = \frac{\exp(y_s \Delta t) - d}{u - d} \quad (\text{B6})$$

$$u = \frac{\exp(2y_s \Delta t) \exp(\sigma^2 \Delta t) + 1 + \sqrt{(\exp(2y_s \Delta t) \exp(\sigma^2 \Delta t) + 1)^2 - 4 \exp(2y_s \Delta t)}}{2 \exp(y_s \Delta t)} \quad (\text{B7})$$

$$d = \frac{\exp(2y_s \Delta t) \exp(\sigma^2 \Delta t) + 1 - \sqrt{(\exp(2y_s \Delta t) \exp(\sigma^2 \Delta t) + 1)^2 - 4 \exp(2y_s \Delta t)}}{2 \exp(y_s \Delta t)} \quad (\text{B8})$$

There are many ways to approximate equations (B7) and (B8). The most well-known one is the Cox, Ross, and Rubinstein (1979) type approximation that is up to order Δt accuracy and is given by

$$u = \exp(\sigma \sqrt{\Delta t}) \quad (\text{B9})$$

$$d = \exp(-\sigma \sqrt{\Delta t}) \quad (\text{B10})$$

Equations (B6), (B9) and (B10) specify the binomial risky tree parameters that are used to map the continuous stock price dynamics into the lattice representation.

Suppose that there is a convertible bond. Let us construct a trading strategy $H = (\alpha, \beta)$ to hold α units of the risky stock and β units of the risky bond. At time t_i the convertible bond value is $C(t_i) = C_B(t_i) + C_S(t_i)$ where $C_B(t_i)$ is the bond component and $C_S(t_i)$ is the stock component; the stock value is $S(t_i)$; and the bond value is $B(t_i)$. At time t_{i+1} , the bond value becomes $B(t_i) \exp(y_b \Delta t)$ where

$y_b = r + h(1 - \varphi_b)$ is the risky rate of the bond; the stock value becomes either $uS(t_i)$ or $dS(t_i)$; and the convertible value has two possible outcomes: $C^u(t_{i+1}) = C_B^u(t_{i+1}) + C_E^u(t_{i+1})$ or $C^d(t_{i+1}) = C_B^d(t_{i+1}) + C_E^d(t_{i+1})$ corresponding to either an up movement or a down movement in the stock price. The discounted portfolio should replicate the discounted convertible bond⁴, which yields

$$\alpha_{i+1}uS(t_i)\exp(-y_s\Delta t) + \beta_{i+1}B(t_i) = C_B^u(t_{i+1})\exp(-y_b\Delta t) + C_S^u(t_{i+1})\exp(-y_s\Delta t) \quad (\text{B11})$$

$$\alpha_{i+1}dS(t_i)\exp(-y_s\Delta t) + \beta_{i+1}B(t_i) = C_B^d(t_{i+1})\exp(-y_b\Delta t) + C_S^d(t_{i+1})\exp(-y_s\Delta t) \quad (\text{B12})$$

Solving for $\alpha_{i+1}, \beta_{i+1}$ yields

$$\alpha_{i+1} = \frac{C_S^u(t_{i+1}) - C_S^d(t_{i+1})}{S(t_i)(u-d)} + \frac{C_B^u(t_{i+1}) - C_B^d(t_{i+1})}{S(t_i)(u-d)} \exp(y_s\Delta t - y_b\Delta t) \quad (\text{B13})$$

$$\beta_{i+1} = \frac{uC_S^d(t_{i+1}) - dC_S^u(t_{i+1})}{B(t_i)(u-d)} \exp(-y_s\Delta t) + \frac{uC_B^d(t_{i+1}) - dC_B^u(t_{i+1})}{B(t_i)(u-d)} \exp(-y_b\Delta t) \quad (\text{B14})$$

For a self-financing portfolio, the initial wealth needed to finance this strategy (sometimes called the manufacturing cost of the contingent claim) is

$$\begin{aligned} C(t_i) &= C_B(t_i) + C_S(t_i) = \alpha_{i+1}S(t_i) + \beta_{i+1}B(t_i) \\ &= [p_u C_S^u(t_{i+1}) + (1-p_u)C_S^d(t_{i+1})]\exp(-y_s\Delta t) + [p_u C_B^u(t_{i+1}) + (1-p_u)C_B^d(t_{i+1})]\exp(-y_b\Delta t) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B15})$$

where p_u is defined in (B6).

We split equation (B15) into an equity equation and a bond equation, and get

$$C_S(t_i) = [p_u C_S^u(t_{i+1}) + (1-p_u)C_S^d(t_{i+1})]\exp(-y_s\Delta t) \quad (\text{B16})$$

$$C_B(t_i) = [p_u C_B^u(t_{i+1}) + (1-p_u)C_B^d(t_{i+1})]\exp(-y_b\Delta t) \quad (\text{B17})$$

Equations (B16) and (B17) tell us that the fair price of an equity component or a bond component is equal to the expected value of its future payoffs discounted by the associated risky rate. The expected

⁴ Unlike the risk-free tree, the risky tree tries to match the discounted value of the replicating portfolio to the discounted value of the convertible bond in order to catch credit risk properly.

value is calculated using the corresponding values from the latter two nodes (up or down) weighted by the transition probabilities.

C. A comparison of results

Let us now briefly turn to a comparison with previous works. We use a simple example described in Table C1, which is similar to the example used in Tsiveriotis and Fernandes (1998) and Ayache, et al. (2003). We assume that the interest rate, the bond spread, and the volatility are flat. The hazard rate is $0.02/(1-0) = 0.02$. As the call and put prices are quoted using the clean prices, we need to convert them to the dirty prices as

$$P^{dirty}(t) = P^{clean}(t) + AI(t) \quad (C1)$$

where the accrued interest is give by

$$AI(t) = C \frac{\delta(t, t_s)}{\delta(t_e, t_s)} \quad (C2)$$

where C denotes the coupon, $\delta(t_s, s_e)$ denotes the accrual factor or day count fraction for period (t_s, t_e) where $t_s \leq t \leq t_e$, t_s denotes the start time of the accrual period, and t_e denotes the end time of the accrual period. The numerical results are shown in Table C2, from which we can see that our model generates lower results than AVF and TF models.

Table C1. A 5-year convertible bond

Maturity	5 years
Payment frequency	Semiannual
Coupon payment	4
Notional	100
Conversion rule	1 share (ratio) in 0 – 5 years
Clean call price	110 in 2 – 5 years

Clean put price	105 at 3 years
Spot stock price	100
Implied volatility of the convertible	0.2
Interest rate	0.05
Bond spread	0.02
Bond recovery rate	0
Stock recovery rate	0

Table C2. Model comparison results

This table presents the numerical results for model comparison. The Tsiveriotis and Fernandes (1998) model is referred to as the TF model and the Ayache, et al. (2003) model is referred to as the AFV model. The convertible bond is described in Table C1.

Time steps	This model	AFV	TF
200	122.6921	122.7341	124.0025
400	122.6938	122.7333	123.9916
800	122.6961	122.7325	123.9821
1600	122.6953	122.7319	123.9754
3200	122.6952	122.7316	123.9714

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